

INVESTIGATION OF PARTICLE SIZE EFFECT ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF POLYMER/GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES AND CFRP DUE TO CRACK TIP SHIELDING

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Motivation and Outline

Question: Why does the addition of stiff nanoparticles improve fracture toughness in brittle polymers with less than 1 wt% of nanofillers? Why is there a strong particle size effect ?

Research Objective: To develop an experimental/analytical approach to answer these fundamental questions to enhance optimal toughness and fatigue life of composite structures

Outline of Presentation:

- Macroscale Mode I fracture toughness test data for EPON 862 epoxy to investigate toughening effect and size effect due to graphene nanoplatelets (GNP/GOs)
- Development of a fundamental physics-based model to explain the toughening mechanism and GNP size effects at the microscale to predict macroscale toughness increase in polymers

Macro-scale Fracture Experiments to Investigate Crack Shielding Effect

Macro Scale Fracture Experiments

- Compact tension (CT) specimens were manufactured with three different **graphene nanoplatelet** sizes (**median size 0.2, 2, and 5 microns**) for 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.7 wt% in epoxy, respectively
- High shear mixing and sonication were used to ensure good dispersion of GNP in EPON 862 epoxy
- At least five replicate $3 \times 3 \times 0.635$ cm CT specimens were molded according to ASTM D5045-99 standard procedure*

*Ref: Amirahmadi et al., *Composite Structures* 347 (2024) 118420.

Initiation Fracture Toughness and CSERR for EPON862/GNP

Cases	Mean K_{Ic} (MPa-m ^{1/2})	STD K_{Ic}	% Increase in K_{Ic} compared to baseline	Mean G_{Ic} (J/m ²)	STD G_{Ic}	% Increase in G_{Ic} compared to baseline
Baseline Epoxy	0.83	±0.03	-	264.9	±28	-
0.1 wt.% 5μ GnP	0.98	±0.026	18	328.8	±19	24
0.3 wt.% 5μ GnP	1.15	±0.03	38	444.8	±39	70
0.5 wt.% 5μ GnP	1.74	±0.1	110	1005.0	±74	279
0.7 wt.% 5μ GnP	1.46	±0.05	76	691.1	±29	161
0.1 wt.% 2μ GnP	1.06	±0.09	27	336.8	±43	27
0.3 wt.% 2μ GnP	1.27	±0.1	53	500.9	±42	89
0.5 wt.% 2μ GnP	1.86	±0.08	124	1150.9	±69	335
0.7 wt.% 2μ GnP	1.6	±0.05	93	910.8	±103	244
0.1 wt.% 0.2μ GO	2.1	±0.26	153	952.0	±164	260
0.2 wt.% 0.2μ GO	2.34	±0.2	182	1347.2	±262	408
0.25 wt.% 0.2μ GO	2.62	±0.14	216	1556.8	±82	488
0.3 wt.% 0.2μ GO	2.71	±0.12	227	1820.8	±142	587
0.35 wt.% 0.2μ GO	2.26	±0.17	172	1340.8	±87	406
0.4 wt.% 0.2μ GO	1.56	±0.08	88	838.1	±75	216
0.5 wt.% 0.2μ GO	1.52	±0.09	83	843.5	±127	218

GNP Size effect in Mode I Fracture Behavior

Comparison of GNP size effect on Fracture Toughness Comparison of GNP size effect on Fracture Energy

- 227 % increase in peak toughness, and 600 % increase in peak fracture energy for 0.2 micron GO @ 0.3 wt% , in comparison with baseline epoxy (0 wt%) is observed*
- Degradation in toughness enhancement due to particle agglomeration occurs earlier for 0.2 micron GO than for 2 and 5 micron GNP cases.

*Ref: Amirahmadi et al., *Composite Structures* 347 (2024) 118420.

SEM of Fracture Surface Morphology

Fracture surface of **baseline specimen** (only epoxy resin) at (a) 500x and (b) 5000x magnification

Fracture surface of **0.3 wt.% 5 μm size graphene reinforced epoxy composites**

SEM of Fracture Surface Morphology

Fracture surface of 0.3 wt.% 2 μm size graphene reinforced epoxy composites

Fracture surface of 0.3 wt.% 0.2 μm size graphene reinforced epoxy composites

The 0.2 μm GO reinforced samples has a rougher morphology as compared with the baseline samples indicating **extensive damage** in FPZ at **crack initiation**, and crack deflection during **crack propagation**

TEM Imaging for GNP Dispersion

TEM images of dispersed nanographene platelets and graphene oxide in epoxy:
(a) 5 μm GNP at 0.3 wt%, (b) 2 μm GNP at 0.3 wt% , and (c) 0.2 μm GO at 0.3 wt%

Good level of exfoliation and dispersion are observed

Modeling of Particle Size Effect on Crack Initiation Toughness using Mechanism Based Approach

Conventional Modeling of Toughening Mechanism Polymer Nanocomposite with Dispersed Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNP)*

1. The macroscale crack impinges on nanographene platelet and deflects
2. After deflection, the fracture process zone (FPZ) consists of cracks at two levels
3. The two cracks coalesce through a shear failure mechanism in the process zone
 - This explanation may be applicable during crack growth but not during crack initiation as it assumes a running crack, because deflection/coalescence can occur only after crack growth.
 - The effect of platelet size is not included in this explanation, as larger GNP size should give rise to higher toughness

*Chandrasekaran, S., Sato, N., Tölle, F., Mülhaupt, R., Fiedler, B., and Schulte, K. "Fracture toughness and failure mechanism of graphene based epoxy composites," Composites Science and Technology, Vol. 97, 2014, pp. 90-99.

A New Approach to Initiation Toughness Modeling in Nanocomposites

- Addition of nanoparticles transforms a brittle epoxy into a quasi-brittle material by inducing damage in the Fracture Process Zone (FPZ) near the crack-tip[1]. This results in two mechanisms:
 - (a) Crack-tip shielding due to the reduction in local modulus caused by debonding (+ve effect)
 - (b) Micro-damage could decrease local initiation toughness near the crack tip (-ve effect)
- These two competing effects determine overall initiation fracture toughness of the nanocomposite in this model [2]

Fracture Process Zone (FPZ) with micro-damage for thermoset polymer with randomly dispersed graphene nanoplatelets (GNP)[1].

- [1] Failure behavior and scaling of graphene nanocomposites, Cory Mefford, Yao Qiao, Marco Salviato, Composite Structures 176 (2017) 961–972
[2] G. Ravichandran et al. Crack Tip Shielding in Elastic Particulate Composites undergoing Damage, Eng. Fract. Mech. Vol. 59, No. 6, pp. 713-723,

Three zones in a nanocomposite that give rise to crack-tip shielding under far-field loading*

*[1] A.G. Evans, S. Williams, and P.W.R. Beaumont, On the Toughness of Particulate Filled Polymers, *Journal of Material Science* 20 (1985), 3668-3674.

[2] G. Ravichandran, and C.T. Liu, Crack Tip Shielding in Elastic Particulate Composites undergoing Damage, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* Vol. 59, No. 6, pp. 713-723, 1998.

Partitioning of Far-field Stress Intensity as a Product of Crack-tip Shielding and Local Toughness Change Near the Crack tip in Epoxy

From path independence of J – integral^{*}, $J_{Nctip} = J_{N.C.FF}$ *J.R. Rice, Journal of Applied Mechanics 1968

$$\text{But for plane stress, } J = \frac{K^2}{E}$$

$$\frac{K_{Nctip}^2}{E_{Nctip}} = \frac{K_{N.C.FF}^2}{E_{N.C.FF}}$$

$$\text{In general, } K_{N.C.FF} = K_{Nctip} \sqrt{\frac{E_{N.C.FF}}{E_{Nctip}}}$$

$$\text{At fracture, } K_{IC,N.C.FF} = K_{IC,Nctip} \sqrt{\frac{E_{N.C.FF}}{E_{Nctip}}}$$

- The second factor on the R.H.S., $\sqrt{\frac{E_{N.C.FF}}{E_{Nctip}}}$, denotes the crack-tip shielding contribution
- The first factor on the R.H.S., $K_{IC,Nctip}$, is the actual local toughness at the tip of the macroscale crack in the presence of microcracks induced by nanofillers in the FPZ, and is a measure of the local toughness change due to micro-damage caused by the nanofillers
- These two competing effects determine overall far-field toughness of nanocomposite!

Model Development for Crack-tip Shielding and Local Toughness Change in Epoxy

$$K_{IC,N.C.FF} = K_{IC,Nctip} \sqrt{\frac{E_{N.C.FF}}{E_{Nctip}}}$$

$$E_{Nctip} = E_{epoxy} (K_{ICM}^2 / K_{ICN.C.FF}^2) = E_{epoxy} (1 - \beta n^q)$$

Where, K_{ICM} is the epoxy toughness, $E_{epoxy} = 1.68$ GPa is the elastic modulus of the undamaged epoxy matrix without GNP, β ($V_f GNP$) and q are power-law parameters, and n is the number density of GNP particles

$$\text{Assuming, } K_{IC,Nctip} = K_{ICM} (1 - V_{fGNP})$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_{ICN.C.FF} &= K_{ICM} (1 - V_{fGNP}) \sqrt{\frac{E_{N.C.FF}}{E_{epoxy} (1 - \beta n^q)}} \\ &= K_{ICM} (1 - V_{fGNP}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{E_{epoxy}}{E_{N.C.FF}} \left[1 - \beta \left(\frac{V_{fGNP}}{l_p^2 t_p} \right)^q \right]}} \end{aligned}$$

Where, l_p is the median particle size, and t_p is the median particle thickness.

MODEL PREDICTIONS

Comparison of Model Toughness Prediction for CT Specimens at RT

- Good agreement is observed between model prediction and actual CT test data
- The smaller the particle size greater is the toughness increase due to shielding effect
- Predicts 227 % **maximum** toughness increase with 0.2 micron GNP at 0.3 wt%
- The model is able to capture the peak increase in toughness before degradation due to agglomeration can set in. This enables unique prediction of optimum toughness!

Comparison of Model Toughness Prediction for CT Specimens at RT

Comparison with Test Data from Shirodkar et al.* for GNP/Epon862 Nanocomposite

Specimen	K_{Ic} (MPa.m ^{0.5})	Normalized K_{Ic}	Model Prediction	Percentage Difference
Baseline epoxy	0.75	1.0	1.0	0
0.1 wt % 5 μ m GNP in epoxy	1.1	1.4667	1.1667	-20.5
0.5 wt % 5 μ m GNP in epoxy	1.58	2.1067	2.0714	-1.7

*Ref: Shirodkar N, Cheng S, Seidel GD. Enhancement of Mode I fracture toughness properties of epoxy reinforced with graphene nanoplatelets and carbon nanotubes. Composites B Eng 2021;224.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.109177>.

Optimum Model Predictions Including Cut-Off Due to Agglomeration

- Using only 10 data points for model calibration, the model can predict optimum GNP size and number density required for maximum toughness enhancement
- Predicts 310 % maximum toughness increase with 0.6 micron GNP size at 0.32 wt%

**GNP SIZE EFFECT IN DELAMINATION
TOUGHNESS ENHANCEMENT FOR
CARBON COMPOSITE**

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) Test for Measuring Mode I Delamination Toughness *

- Unidirectional IM7/EPON-862 laminates tested as per ASTM D5528 clearly indicate particle size effect as shown in the chart ; coating carbon fabric enhances toughness
- The enhancement in fracture energy is lower for the carbon composite as the toughened matrix causes the crack to partly propagate along the fiber-matrix interface

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) Results for Mode I Delamination Toughness

- Unidirectional IM7/EPON-862 laminates tested indicate particle size effect as shown in the chart with up to 180 % improvement over baseline case at initiation
- The enhancement in fracture energy is slightly lower for the carbon composite as the toughened matrix causes the crack to propagate along the fiber-matrix interface

SEM IMAGES OF DCB FRACTURE SURFACE FOR BASELINE CASE AND 0.2 Micron GO AT 0.3 wt%

Baseline Laminate

Laminate with 0.2 micron GO at 0.3 wt%

SEM images show evidence of cohesive fracture in the polymer in the case of baseline laminate (without GNP) but crack propagates along the fiber-matrix interface for GO case

- Toughening of fiber-matrix interface in addition to matrix toughening will therefore improve overall composite delamination toughness

Summary and Conclusions

- This paper presents clear evidence of the influence of GNP size on fracture toughness and CSERR in GNP/EPON862 as well as IM7/EPON862/GNP composite
- Our test data reveals a 227% peak enhancement (that is, 3.23 times improvement from the baseline value) in mode I fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and 587% peak enhancement in G_{ic} over the baseline epoxy for specimens with 0.2 μm GO at 0.3 wt.% , likely due to crack tip shielding.
- The enhancement in G_{ic} for the DCB specimens show similar size effect, although the degree of toughness enhancement was lower (~180%) due to debond failure
- Fracture toughness enhancement is observed to decrease with higher wt % of GNP
- An analytical model based on crack-tip shielding due to number density of GNP particles was developed and verified with test data (A patent was filed in 2023).
- Our future work will attempt to study these mechanisms in detail using in-situ AFM and/or SEM which will be used in conjunction with 2-D digital image correlation (DIC) to obtain local in-plane strain maps to provide a clearer understanding of crack shielding mechanisms in the fracture process zone, and crack propagation

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